

Leptospirosis Associated with Swimming

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Swimming has grown massively in popularity in recent times. Not only swimming outdoors a pleasant way to enjoy the sunshine, fresh air and green leafy surroundings, it can also help to relieve stress and elevate our endorphins. This creates a sense of wellbeing as well as burning calories and exercising muscles. But along with the joys of outdoor swimming come some dangers. Not only swimmers were more at risk from tides, currents and swells, there can also be nasty bugs and bacteria lurking in the water, seas, rivers and lakes. Of course, swimming in a pool comes with its own set of risks.

Rats living in sewers adjacent to freshwater rivers or canals can also carry in their urine the bacterial pathogen *Leptospira*, which causes Leptospirosis (Weil's disease). The infection occurs if soil or water from a lake, river or canal that contains urine from infected animals is swallowed, gets in a swimmer's eyes or a cut.

Leptospirosis can cause liver and kidney damage, and may be fatal if left untreated. If you develop flu or jaundice symptoms up to two weeks after swimming in a river or canal, it may be a good idea to ask your doctor for a Leptospirosis test.

Introduction:

Leptospirosis is a worldwide zoonosis caused by spirochetes from the genus *Leptospira*. It is wide spread bacterial zoonotic disease in world. It is an emerging infectious disease. Acute anthro-po-zoonotic infection. Most common in tropical and subtropical areas with high rainfall. The disease is found mainly wherever humans come into contact with the urine of infected

animals or a urine-polluted environment. Aftermath of natural disasters. Outbreaks in rural / semi urban settings. 7 – 10 million infected annually. Mostly affected are the South- East Asian countries. Acute bacterial infection caused by spirochetes of genus *Leptospira* that can lead to multiple organ involvement and fatal complications. Leptospire enter the body via small cuts or abrasions, through mucous membranes such as the conjunctiva and through wet skin. Outbreaks of Leptospirosis have been associated with common water events such as rural and urban flooding, swimming, and other water sports as well as occupational exposure involved predominantly with farming and drinking contaminated water.

Classification:

The genus *Leptospira* comprises both pathogenic and non-pathogenic species, with the main pathogenic species being *Leptospira interrogans* and the non-pathogenic species being *Leptospira biflexa*

Morphology:

Gram negative, actively motile, helical rod shaped bacteria with ends- Bent/ hooked. Locomotion is by rotation, flexion and extension.

Fig.1. Helical rod shaped *Leptospira* Transmission:

Leptospirosis is a worldwide zoonosis affecting many wild and domestic animals. Humans acquire the infection by contact with the urine of infected animals. Human-to-human transmission is extremely rare. Rodents, particularly rats, are significant reservoirs of *Leptospira* bacteria, the causative agent of leptospirosis, and can transmit the disease through urine contaminated water, soil, or direct contact.

Diagnosis:

- History and clinical signs.
- Dark field microscopy examination of urine or serum (examined immediately after collection), at early stage of the disease.
- Microscopic agglutination test: It is a 'gold standard test' as per OIE. Positive titre is 1:100.
- Culture and identification in EMJH (Ellinghausen McCullough Johnson and Harris) medium.

Fig.2. Transmission of Leptospirosis

- On semisolid or liquid medium, the growth of Leptospire is described as Dinger's ring. Other media that can also be used are, Korthof's medium, Stuart's medium, Fletcher's medium and Vervoort's medium.
- Culture is difficult and requires several weeks.
- Molecular diagnosis by PCR.
- Antibody detection in serum and aqueous humor.
- A rapid diagnosis is made with the Dot-ELISA test.
- IgM antibody detection ELISA is most useful for early diagnosis of clinical leptospirosis. Silver impregnation staining (Fontana's staining and Levaditi's staining) can be used to stain Leptospire in tissue section.

• Hematology

- Hemolytic anemia.
- Haemoglobinuria.
- Increased BUN, bilirubin, leucocytic count and erythrocytic fragility.

Treatment:

Antibiotics such as penicillin or tetracycline or doxycycline can be used.

Prevention and control:

- Vaccination of animals, particularly cattle, dogs and swine.
- Chemoprophylaxis of animals with Dihydrostreptomycin @25 mg/kg body weight. • Rodent control.
- Avoid walking bare foot in contaminated or stagnant water.
- Avoid swimming in or drinking from potentially contaminated water. (To avoid leptospirosis while swimming, avoid

Fig.3.Prevention of Leptospirosis

swimming in water that might be contaminated with animal urine, especially after heavy rainfall or flooding, and cover any cuts or scratches with waterproof bandages).

- Protect workers by providing boots and gloves.
- Doxycycline- chemoprophylaxis for persons at high exposure.
- Mass education to create awareness.